

METHODS OF TEACHING THE TOPIC "CHARACTERISTICS OF MUSHROOMS" TO STUDENTS OF THE ACADEMIC LYCEUM BASED ON B-B-B TECHNOLOGY.

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Abstract. Mushrooms decompose waste and prevent its excessive accumulation. They also return mineral salts needed by plants to the soil. Some mushrooms are used in the production of medicinal substances and help a person fight diseases. Other fungi cause diseases in plants and animals. Man is always forced to fight them.

Key words: plant herbariums, mold, Fusarium, black moth, rust fungus, laboratory, fungal mycelium, spores, microscopes, magnifiers.

Аннотация. Замбуруғлар чиқиндиларни чиритади ва уларнинг ҳаддан зиёд тўпланиб қолишига монелик қилади. Улар тупроққа ўсимликлар учун зарур бўлган минерал тузларни ҳам қайтаради. Айрим замбуруғлар дори моддалар ишлаб чиқаришда қўл келади ва инсонга касалликларга қарши курашишда ёрдам беради.

Бошқа замбуруғлар эса ўсимликлар ва ҳайвонларда касаллик келтириб чиқаради. Инсон доимо уларга қарши курашишга мажбур.

Калит сўзлар: ўсимлик гербарийлари, моғор, фузариум, қора куя, занг замбуруғи, лаборатория, замбуруғ мицелийси, спора, микроскоплар, лупалар.

Абстрактный. Грибы разлагают отходы и препятствуют их чрезмерному накоплению. Также они возвращают в почву минеральные соли, необходимые растениям. Некоторые грибы используются в производстве лекарственных веществ и помогают человеку бороться с болезнями.

Другие грибы вызывают заболевания растений и животных. Человек всегда вынужден бороться с ними.

Ключевые слова: гербарии растений, плесень, фузариоз, черная моль, ржавчинный гриб, лаборатория, грибной мицелий, споры, микроскопы, лупы.

“**B-B-B**” - I know, I want to know, I found out- **The table** allows students to search by topic, text, section . Develops students' skills of systematic thinking, structuring, and analysis. Before the start of the lesson, the teacher familiarizes the students with the rule of making a schedule. The group is divided into separate subgroups and introduced to the procedure for drawing up the schedule.

They answer the questions "What do you know about the topic" and "What do you want to know?" They listen to the lecture, read independently, independently, in small groups, fill in 3 sections of the table

Scientific goal: to explain the types of nutrition (saprotroph, parasite) and their importance in the characteristics of fungi, to teach the ways of their spread in soil formation and nature .

Educational purpose: based on the study of the biological properties of fungi, to teach their place in the cycle of substances in nature, their importance in causing various diseases in plants and increasing soil fertility.

Developmental goal: To develop knowledge and skills about the conditions of living in the soil, the causes of plant disease, their beneficial and harmful properties in agriculture, biology, morphology and other signs, based on getting to know the feeding methods of fungi.

Necessary equipment: Morphological structure of mold, fusarium, black moth, rust fungi, tables showing feeding methods, test tubes with fungal mycelium, diseased plant herbariums, microscopes, magnifying glasses, slide glass, cover glass.

After the scientific, educational and development purpose of the new topic, information about the necessary equipment, the B-B-B technology used in the lesson and the procedure for its execution are explained to the students, before the lesson

is explained, the students are asked to write down their understanding of lines 1-2, and it is said that they should underline it. . Then, after the topic is explained to the students, in order to determine how much they have mastered the lesson, under the line drawn in the “B-B-B” technology, the newly acquired knowledge, concepts and questions they want to know are written. In doing so, we can determine the result of mastering a new topic using the “B-B-B” technology. That is, whoever has mastered the subject well, he writes down as much knowledge as he has learned. Students who have fully mastered the knowledge can be evaluated with a higher score.

How to do the work: Before starting the laboratory session, students are asked the following questions: What kind of organisms are fungi? What types of fungi are divided according to the method of nutrition? What do you understand by heterotrophic nutrition? What types of fungi are saprotrophic? What are the types of parasitic fungi? What types of fungi are facultatively parasitic?

1. Observe the mycelium, band of sporangia, sporangia and spores of a mold fungus fed by the saprotrophic method under a microscope. Watch a piece of bread that has grown mold fall apart. Watch the fungal spores grow on Chapeka nutrient medium.
2. Observe the mycelium, macro- and microconidia and chlamydospores of the fungus in the preparation of Fusarium fungus, which causes leaf rot disease.
3. Learn about wheat ear damage caused by black moth, a parasite that feeds on wheat grain. Pay attention to the external structure of the wheat grain, the shape of the fungal spores that form inside the grain.
4. Observe the spores of the black moth fungus first in the small lens of the microscope, and then in the large lens, pay attention to the color of the spore skin, the structure of the surface, and its small size.
5. To know the damage of parasitic fungi, pay attention to the shape, color, and size of healthy and black moth-infected seeds.

Task: Draw a picture of a colony of a mold fungus that feeds saprotrophically, a

sporangium band, sporangia and spores formed from its mycelium.

Draw a picture of the uredospores formed on and inside the wheat grain of the parasitic black moth fungus.

Draw a picture of the mycelium, macro and microconidia of the fungus Fusarium from representatives of the facultative parasitic fungus.

Using this method, students of group I of Qibray Academic Lyceum completed the BBB table as follows (example).

the topic "Characteristics of fungi" based on the "B-B-B" technology

I know	I want to know	Knowing i got
<p>Fungi are microscopic organisms. They are autotrophic organisms. Causes diseases. Fungi cannot be seen with the naked eye.</p>	<p>What is the name of the body of the mold fungus. How do fungi feed? What diseases does Fusarium fungus cause? What are the types of black moth fungus? What part of wheat does the rust fungus infect? How does rust fungus reproduce? How saprotrophs break down nutrients. What enzymes do fungi produce? How parasites feed. What changes take place in the diseased plant. What happens when the spore of the fungus grows? What do fungi produce when they reproduce</p>	<p>The body of fungi is called mycelium. It is fed on the basis of ready-made organic matter. Root rot disease is caused by Fusarium fungus. There are two types of black moth fungus, powdery black moth and solid black moth. Rust fungus damages wheat leaf and stem. Rust fungus reproduces asexually by forming pads. Breaks down nutrients with the help of enzymes. Fungi produce enzymes that break down woody tissue Parasitic fungi feed on ready-made organic matter in the cell.</p>

	asexually?	Sporangium band, sporangium and spore are formed from mycelium. When fungi reproduce asexually, they form mycelium, micro- and macroconidia, spores.
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After the students have completed the third column of the table, the teacher asks the students to read the questions they want to know and to return scientific answers to each question based on their knowledge and skills. For example:

The mold fungus causes the bread to mold in the home conditions, plant remains rot in the soil. *Mucor mucedo* Fres is among the fungi belonging to this category in the conditions of our republic. *Emend Bref.*, the type plays a major role in bread mold and humus enrichment of the soil. Enzymes help these fungi to feed saprotrophically. Their amylase enzyme breaks down the starch in the bread and turns it into glucose.

What are the types of Fusarium fungus? A. Sheraliev (1974-2017) studied fungi belonging to the Fusarium family found in the conditions of our republic.

Representatives of this group form a colorless widespread mycelium and form macro- and microconidia in conidia bands, heads, and chains. The shape of the conidia is ellipsoidal, pencil-shaped, sickle-shaped, lemon-shaped, ovoid, and has 1-7 septa.

Representatives of this group are facultative parasitic fungi, the saprotrophic species include *Fusarium solani*, the parasitic species include *Fusarium oxysporum*, and they cause wilt disease in cotton plants. The toxins produced by the parasite kill the plant.

What are the types of black moth fungus? In the conditions of Uzbekistan, there are two types of black moth: solid black moth (*Tilletia lives*) and powdery black moth (*Ustilago tritici*). These species live in the soil, enter the stem through

the root of the plant and develop in the bud of the flower in the spike. It forms dark brown chlamydo spores by feeding on the accumulated nutrients in the grain formed from the nodule. These spores cause the fungus to spread.[3]

How saprotrophs break down nutrients. Saprotrophic fungi create enzymes that break down the plant cell wall. These enzymes break down the organic substances included in the plant and create sugar. Saprotrophic fungi gain nutritional properties due to the sugar produced.

What role do enzymes made by fungi play? Enzymes are an important step in the decomposition of organic matter in nature, and play a key role in the formation of mineral substances in the soil in the nutrition of plants.

How do parasites feed on fungi? Parasitic fungi feed on ready-made organic matter produced in the host plant cell.

What changes take place in an infected plant? Liver or brown and black spots of various sizes appear on the leaves, stems, and spikes of plants infected with fungi. The plant lags behind in growth and development. The disease completely kills the plant in periods of strong development.

The following test tasks are given in order to determine the level of students' mastery of the lesson topic explained on the basis of the B-B-B method.

TEST

1. How do fungi feed?
A. Saprotroph; B. parasite; V. Facultative parasite; G. All answers are correct;
2. Show the fungi that feed saprotroph.
A. Mukor; B. Black moth; V. Rust; G. Fusarium.
3. Show the fungi on which the parasite feeds.
A. Mukor; B. Black moth; V. Rust; G. B and V;.
4. Show facultative parasitic fungi.
A. Mukor; B. Black moth; V. Rust; G. Fusarium.
5. What role do saprophytic fungi play in nature?

A. Decomposes plant residues; B. Causes disease in plants; V. Not important; G. Breaks down salts.

6. What diseases do parasitic fungi cause?

A. Black moth; B. rust; V.A and B; G. Does not cause disease.

7. What role do facultative parasitic fungi play in nature?

A. Decomposes plant residues in the soil; B. Diseases the plant; V.A and B; G. It does not play any role in nature.

8. How do fungi multiply?

A. Forming spores; B. Produces macro and microconidia; With the help of V. Mitseli; G. All answers are correct

9. How do fungi break down organic matter?

A. Using teeth; B. Using enzymes; With the help of V. Mitseli; with the help of G. Spora.

10. How do parasites feed?

A. At the expense of ready-made organic substances in the cell; Through B. Bargi; V. Through the root; G. All answers are correct.

After the students solve the test questions on the topic, the teacher answers the questions in the third column of the table, completes the lesson and evaluates the students.

Appendix 2

Evaluation criteria and indicators

Groups	Complete and clear clarification of the question 0-5 points	Finding a solution to the problem with examples is 0-5 points	Group of members activity 0-5 points	Total score
I group				
II group				

III group				
Group IV				

15 - 13 points - "excellent".

12 - 10 points - "good".

9 - 6 points - "satisfactory".

USED LITERATURE

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